

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

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Abbreviation list

DMP	Data Management Plan
DPEC	Data Protection and Ethics Coordinator
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EAB	External Advisory Board
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR	EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679
OA	Open Access
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot

Executive Summary

Deliverable 1.1 – Data Management Plan (DMP) is related to *WP1 – Coordination and management, Task 1.4 - Data protection, data management plan and ethics compliance*. Task 1.4 runs for the entire duration of the project to ensure that the implementation of *reCreating Europe* adheres to the EU legal and normative framework, as well as to key ethical and societal values and principles. *ReCreating Europe's* Compliance Framework (CF) is developed as a structured set of guidelines covering the broadest possible spectrum of legal and ethical issues arising during the development of the project, considering, in particular, the rights of all relevant stakeholders and actors, both as end-users and as participants in surveys, workshops, and semi-structured interviews.

This DMP records the procedures for data management within the *reCreating Europe* project. It documents the types of data the project will generate or collect, the standards and platforms that will be used for storage and processing, measures to assure legal compliance, and the plan for how these data will be curated and preserved to enable maximal future exploitation, sharing and re-use. It represents the general strategy of *reCreating Europe* Consortium to establish a FAIR ecosystem on research data developed during the project in order to fulfil the Open Research Data Pilot policy.

It has been already identified that several project's research activities will involve human participants, some of them being vulnerable, and the collection and processing of personal data will require the collection of informed consent and ethics clearance. Informed consent and ethical approval procedures and forms are included in *D1.2 Informed consent forms and information sheets*, to be read in conjunction with this document.

This document provides in attachment a detailed list of datasets to be developed in each WP and specifies the rules to be applied for each research data category, in order to identify common rules on how data will be curated and preserved in the long term, and on how they can be collected and stored to make them findable, prepare their reuse, and make them openly accessible and interoperable.

The document is divided into the following sections:

- Methodology (Section 1)
- Standards, guidance and legislation (Section 2)
- Data summary (Section 3)
- Conclusions (Section 4).

This deliverable is written in Month 3 of the project and is intended to be a 'live' document that is updated as the project progresses. A record of the changes will be made in the version and contribution history.

1. Methodology

The development of the Data Management Plan consisted of three different steps.

Firstly, the task leader prepared a short presentation on Data Management Plan and Open Research Data Pilot in order to introduce the main principles, challenges, and objectives of the Deliverable. In particular, the presentation included a description of the FAIR principles, the contents to be included in the DMP, and the workplan activities. This activity achieved two main purposes: to provide awareness on the general framework on this management activity, and to provide specific instructions tailored to *reCreating Europe*.

Secondly, the task leader shared a form in order to collect the proper information from each partner. For each WP, the DMP form included a description of the dataset that will be developed, processed, shared, etc. during *reCreating Europe's* research activities (**Annex 1**).

Thirdly, from the analysis of the shared DMP form, the task leader extracted the rules to be applied for the project data management, considering the Open Research Data Pilot purposes and exceptions (i.e. IPRs and data protection issues, the need to prevent misuse of research results, and other possible commercial interests that have to be balanced against the main purposes of the open access policy).

ReCreating Europe's data management procedures comply with the internal policies of participating universities and institutions, with national and EU legislation and with H2020 guidelines. They will be rigorously applied, irrespective of the country in which the research is carried out.

Data may be collected, stored and used only by members of the *reCreating Europe* consortium, which consists of:

1. SCUOLA SUPERIORE DI STUDI UNIVERSITARI E DI PERFEZIONAMENTO SANT'ANNA (SSSA)
2. UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM (UVA)
3. UNIVERSITY OF GLASGOW (UGLA)
4. ALEXANDER VON HUMBOLDT-INSTITUT FÜR INTERNET UND GESELLSCHAFT GMBH (HIIG)
5. STICHTING LIBER (LIBER)
6. NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND MAYNOOTH (NUIM)
7. TARTU ULIKOOL (UTARTU)
8. UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI TRENTO (UNITN)
9. KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET (UCPH)
10. SZEGEDI TUDOMÁNYEGYETEM (USZ)

As part of *reCreating Europe* consortium's commitment to responsible research practices, the Consortium Agreement includes the partners' commitment to FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) data management practices. The External Advisory Board (EAB) will provide additional oversight of the process.

2. Standards, guidance and legislation

The design of studies will adhere to the Helsinki Declaration and the Ethics of Information and Communication Technologies report (2012) from the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies to the EC. We will also conform to the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU and to the current legislative framework in the field of data protection.

The new European General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679¹ (GDPR) came into force on 24 May 2016 and, following a two-year implementation phase, applies from 25 May 2018. EU Member States were expected to adapt their previous national laws according to the GDPR by 6 May 2018 and to introduce in some cases, like the ones related to data processing for research purposes, some national safeguards and derogations. The regulation updated legislation to ensure that people's right to personal data protection remains effective in the digital age. The project partners will ensure that all future project research activities are compliant with the GDPR and national data protection laws still in force.

As far as the British partner is concerned, Brexit is not currently affecting the applicable legal framework on data protection, as the so-called transition period, where the GDPR and the Data Protection Act are still in force, has just started. In the next months it is possible that the British Data Protection framework will be approved in terms of adequacy decision under Article 45 GDPR by the EU Commission. In any case, the Consortium will pay attention to these evolutions, including the opinions and guidelines issued by the European Data Protection Board and the Information Commissioner's Office, in order to promptly address the data management strategy and implement any possible organizational and technical measures to ensure reCreating Europe's full compliance with the regulatory framework.

According to Article 29.3 of the Grant Agreement, the development of *reCreating Europe's* concept and objectives will be available in terms of **open access research data**.

As far as research data are concerned, the open access policy will be limited only in the following circumstances:

- *Data protection issues*: personal data belonging to volunteers will be collected, stored, and processed following the procedures described under D1.1. and D1.2 in compliance with the current EU and national legal framework (EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679, GDPR).
- *Public safety (misuse)*: the Consortium will prevent any possible misuse of research outputs, also by deciding not to make some of the research outputs available in open access.
- *Intellectual property (IP) rights*: the Consortium will identify possible limits descending from the IP protection of its results or data and dataset used to achieve the individual purposes of the project.
- *Commercial interests*: the Consortium might evaluate possible commercial exploitation of the project's results.

These four cases are considered as exceptions to the CC BY NC 4.0 licence by which third parties may share (*i.e.* copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (*i.e.* remix, transform, and build upon) the material for any purpose, even commercially.

The Open Access research data include the establishment of a FAIR ecosystem:

- **Findable**: the repository offers easy and user-friendly search features.
- **Accessible**: the search mask identifies access rules for each research data uploaded (e.g. authentication).
- **Interoperable**: datasets or research data will be uploaded considering the opportunity to be integrated with other datasets/research data.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.119.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2016:119:TOC

- **Reusable:** a homogeneous description of data (therefore metadata) increases the opportunity to replicate and/or combine data following the open licence.

This **FAIR** ecosystem will be achieved through the following strategy:

- the Consortium opened a “Community” referred to *reCreating Europe* on the Zenodo repository. This will allow the collection and storage of research data following the OpenAIRE standards for EU Commission funded projects. The community is accessible here <https://zenodo.org/communities/recreatingeurope/?page=1&size=20> and it will be managed and populated by the project partners under the supervision of the Data Protection and Ethics Coordinator (DPEC) (**Annex 2**).
- the dissemination and communication activities will contribute in synergy to the Open Access Research Pilot by boosting the publication and sharing of research outputs on *reCreating Europe*’s communication channels (i.e. *reCreating Europe* website, social channels etc.)

As far as publications are concerned, the Consortium opted for promoting the Open Access policy as long as this is feasible and convenient considering the target and the rank of the given journal/publisher. In any case, each Partner will make sure that the selected publisher/journal allows the open access sharing of the preprint version of publications stemming from the project’s research activities.

The **Data Protection and Ethics Coordinator (DPEC)**, appointed by the Project Coordinator (PC) upon the approval of the Project Management Board (PMB) in the person of Giovanni Comandé (SSSA), will be in charge of reviewing the management and handling of ethical issues in the course of *reCreating Europe*’s activities. The DPEC will guide consortium partners in the DMP implementation, will monitor and make sure that the DMP procedures are correctly and fairly implemented, and will give feedback and opinions to the PC on any ethical issues and questions that may arise during the performance of the project’s activities and their implementation. The DPEC will perform the review of the DMP at least every six months, and every time ethical questions are referred, ex se or in the context of risk management procedures, by the PC, the PMB, and/or WP leaders.

At a consortium member level, data protection compliance will be assessed by the institutional Data Protection Officers and by the institutional Research Ethics Boards or Committees as required by national legislations.

The DPEC and the PMB will continuously monitor ethical data management procedures and will keep record of all potential ethical issues arising as the project is delivered. A list of key relevant guides and publications will be maintained. The procedures will be reviewed at key milestones, including before the commencement of each WP.

The research methods that will be used in *reCreating Europe* do not include any methods that are usually associated with **incidental findings** (ie “*findings concerning an individual research participant that has potential health or reproductive importance and is discovered in the course of conducting research but is beyond the aims of the study*”) such as genetic research, brain and body imaging, or medical tests. In the unlikely event that an incidental finding that can be associated with an identifiable participant does occur in the course of *reCreating Europe*, the Consortium will follow a standard protocol considering the partner’s Institutional research ethics board that originally approved the research ones and the DPEC will be informed. Furthermore, should it happen that in the course of the research a partner incidentally collects information or data that appears to disclose criminal or illegal activity, it will follow the relevant national legislation in the country where the research is being carried out. Where the law is silent or incomplete, guidance from the Institutional Data Protection Officer/institutional Ethics Board or Committee that approved the research will be sought. The Consortium will prepare an internal protocol on confidentiality and on the responsibility of

researchers when incidentally confronted with information that may appear to relate to criminal or illegal activity. The protocol will follow these criteria:

- each researcher will be committed to his/her own institutional code of ethics.
- each researcher will be committed to specific confidential obligations during the personal data collection, processing, and storage.
- questionnaires will be designed in order to avoid any possible direct answers on facts which might be related to disclosing any criminal or illegal activity.
- in case of free text answers users will be informed that the content will be analysed for research purposes and the institutional code of ethics will be applied, considering the technical and organizational measures applied to pseudonymised data.
- the system administrator will provide to report breaches to the competent authorities under the applicable legal framework.

further tailored advice will be provided by the DPEC when each participatory activity will be designed.

3. Data summary

As stated, the DMP is a living document which may be updated by the partners during *reCreating Europe's* implementation under the ordinary management activities. Considering the nature of the project, the general strategy shall be applicable to five identified categories of research data: (1) deliverables, (2) scientific articles, (3) surveys, (4) the stakeholder platform, (5) communication and dissemination tools.

In order to better describe the information on how the *reCreating Europe* consortium will collect, structure, analyse and publish data we will consider the following research data that could be produced within one (or more) WP:

- 1) *reCreating Europe's* research data are illustrated in 51 **deliverables**, which include the research data collected and provided in each WP. During the implementation of each deliverable, the research data is stored in a Dropbox Business project shared folder. For each deliverable the preparatory materials are collected in a sub-folder named "work". Deliverables are firstly drafted in word documents, describing how the related tasks have been addressed and which results have been achieved. Then, the final version is printed in .pdf format and submitted to the EU Commission Service. Size will be approximately included between 1M <x <20 M. The deliverable is stored in the Dropbox Business shared folder for all the duration of the project. Furthermore, if the deliverable is public, it will be uploaded, together with the corresponding research data, in the above-mentioned Zenodo platform under CC BY 4.0. licence, as well as in the dedicated section of the project website. If the deliverable is confidential, it will not be accessible to the public but shared only between Consortium members.
- 2) In case the research outputs consist of **scientific articles**, each publication shall maximise the opportunity to publish under a green or gold OA policy. However, considering the main goal to publish the resulting scientific articles in top ranking journals, partners are free to submit papers also under other policies. In any case, partners agree to negotiate at least the free sharing of preprints on repositories that allow their reading, download and printing. References and OA articles will also be available in dedicated sections of the project website in order to allow a more effective dissemination of the research products. In addition, the academic partners have institutional repositories (e.g. Scuola Sant'Anna IRIS <https://www.iris.sssup.it>) that make it possible, as long as authors have institutional accounts, to share their publications within the academic community. Furthermore, *reCreating Europe's* Zenodo Community will be used also as a repository of scientific publications.
- 3) *reCreating Europe's* research activities involve stakeholders through **surveys**. These research data will be governed by the applicable data protection regulation according to ethical requirements.

D.1.2. will include samples of tailored information sheet and informed consent templates to be applied to each stakeholder's category. As far as the management of this kind of research data is concerned, templates will be adapted to each questionnaire and stored in the Consortium shared folder. D.1.2., in fact, is a confidential deliverable. Personal data collected during the surveys will be collected and stored as stated in each privacy information policy, which is part of the information sheet to be shared before administering the questionnaires in order to collect the informed consent. Informed consent sheets will be collected under the conditions provided by the applicable legal framework to the responsible task leader. These administrative records will be accessible in case of ethical audit. The PC will be allowed to ask for a copy or a declaration of compliance from the other partners. Personal data will be processed mostly as pseudonymized data and results will be published only as aggregate or anonymous ones. During the development of the project, Annex 1 will be updated in order to establish the organizational and technical measures necessary to properly store surveys in a homogeneous confidential repository with access limited to authorized researchers. For example, in order to avoid unneeded personal data flows, each task leader will be responsible to collect, process and store data in compliance with the GDPR applicable national implementations. Specific one-to-one advice will be provided by the DPEC.

- 4) *reCreating Europe's* research activities include the development of a **stakeholder platform**, which consists of an online *forum*, where associations and other representative entities may discuss the project's research interim results, comment on draft policy recommendations and best practices, or engage in debates on issues related to the content of the research. At this stage, the forum will be designed as follows. It will be moderated by the researchers involved in the task. Furthermore, apart from the navigation data of the users representing the given association/entity, no personal data will be collected. The results of the discussions may be included in the given deliverables. The platform will be embedded in the project website, and access will be provided upon registration. The platform will include a training toolkit, whose features will be identified according to the Gantt needs. Specific organizational and technical measures will be applied during the development of the platform, which will create an own FAIR ecosystem. As a consequence, the DMP will be integrated during the project.
- 5) Other datasets may be provided through mailing lists, newsletters, social channels according to the **communication and dissemination activities**. In these cases, the administrative procedures of collection, processing and storage will be applied by each involved partner, which will act as data controller in case of personal data. Published data for communication and dissemination purposes will be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable from the website and the project social channels. Datasets including possible contacts of stakeholders will follow the data protection policies: access and sharing will be limited and proportioned to the collection purposes.

Annex 1 shows the current management strategy for each expected dataset to be developed within the project. Updates and amendments to the Data Management strategy will be provided if needed during the regular course of management activities.

4. Conclusions

The Deliverable described the methodology applied by the *reCreating Europe's* Consortium in order to develop the project data management strategy according to the Open Research Data Pilot policy.

In addition, it described both the organisational measures adopted to build up a FAIR ecosystem and the specific exceptions identified to protect personal data, intellectual property rights and other needs of the Consortium.

These rules converged in the so-called Data Management Plan (DMP) of the project, which is a living document to be possibly updated and integrated during the development of *reCreating Europe's* research activities.

References

- Research Data Life cycle by the UK Data Service (2017) (<https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/lifecycle>)
- EC's Guide on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon2020(http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf)
- EC's Open Access Factsheet(<https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-h2020-factsheets>)
- FAIR Checklist (<https://www.force11.org/fairprinciples>)
- S. Hodson et al., FAIR Data Action Plan Interim recommendations and actions from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR data (<https://zenodo.org/record/1285290#.XBEjSi8VRKM>)
- S. Hodson et al. Report of the Commission FAIR Data Expert Group (FAIR Data EG): Turning FAIR into reality (<https://zenodo.org/record/1285272#.XBEjri8VRKM>)
- Creative Commons License <https://creativecommons.org>

Annexes

1. Annex 1 D1.1 - DMP Form
2. Annex 2 D1.1 - Screenshot from Zenodo *reCreating Europe* Community

